

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FONG****FIRST NAME: WAI LOK****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: MS Office 365 Word on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. To start an academic essay, we need to define a thesis statement. Which option best describes the requirements for writing a good thesis statement?
- A thesis statement shall be concise and wise so that it can reveal the significant argument or point of the essay, and the thesis statement shall be further explained by research question(s) that functions as a guide to a major study.¹**
 - A thesis statement is a process to ask which topic shall be studied in a research and then we use the thesis statement to guide the process of research.
 - A thesis statement is the conclusion of the research process, which helps the reader summarise the whole research content.

¹ Kate Larimore Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition, (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 7.

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- A thesis statement is the methodology to indicate the research process, and the research follows this methodology to complete the research process.
2. Which one of the following options is UK English?
- Can, bill, chips, candy.
- Tin, banknote, crisps, sweet.** ²
- Pants, purse, rest room, store.
- Sidewalk, resume, recess, chips.
3. Plagiarism is a serious and also the most common academic misconduct. It is a threat to the research integrity. Which one of the following options best describes the definition of plagiarism?
- Plagiarism is when the writer directly copies the content from another author and pastes it into his/her essay.
- If the writer rephrases another author's content, it should not be considered plagiarism.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.** ³
- Plagiarism is no longer a problem because AI can help students rewrite the content and avoid detecting plagiarism.

² Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition, (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 25–26.

³ *Ibid.*, 34.

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4. Drafting research question(s) can be used as a method for researchers to begin their research projects or dissertations. Which option best describes the definition of a research question?

- Good research question(s) should contribute to a narrow understanding of an issue and satisfy personal curiosity. Moreover, research question(s) can seem trivial or arise unexpectedly.
- Good research question(s) should contribute to a broader understanding of an issue, not just satisfy personal curiosity. Moreover, research question(s) cannot seem trivial or arise unexpectedly.
- Good research question(s) should contribute to a broader understanding of an issue and not satisfy personal curiosity. Moreover, research question(s) cannot seem trivial or arise unexpectedly.
- Good research question(s) should contribute to a broader understanding of an issue, not just satisfy personal curiosity. Moreover, research question(s) can seem trivial or arise unexpectedly.**⁴

5. There are three types of academic sources used in research. Which of the following options is correct?

- Primary sources are original materials with raw data or evidence. Secondary sources are scholarly works based on primary sources to find other points of view and serve as models for own research. Tertiary sources are materials that**

⁴ Kate Larimore Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition, (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 24.

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synthesise secondary sources for general readers to provide a broad overview of a topic but should not be relied upon in scholarly arguments.⁵

- Primary sources are scholarly works based on primary sources to find other points of view and serve as models for one's research. Secondary sources are original materials with raw data or evidence. Tertiary sources are materials that synthesise secondary sources for general readers to provide a broad overview of a topic but should not be relied upon in scholarly arguments.
- Primary sources are original materials with raw data or evidence. Secondary sources are scholarly works based on primary sources to find other points of view and serve as models for one's research. Tertiary sources are materials that synthesise primary sources for general readers to provide a broad overview of a topic but should not be relied upon in scholarly arguments.
- Primary sources are existing materials with raw data or evidence. Secondary sources are scholarly works based on primary sources to find other raw data. Tertiary sources are materials that synthesise secondary sources for general readers to provide a broad overview of a topic but should not be relied upon in scholarly arguments.

6. Which of the following options is correct about the notes-bibliography style and author-date style?

- In author-date style, a superscript number is placed at the end of the sentence where a source is quoted or referred to.

⁵ Ibid., 36.

- In notes-bibliography style, a superscript number is placed at the end of the sentence where a source is quoted or referred to.⁶
- In notes-bibliography style, a parenthetical citation is placed next to the reference to the source.
- In author-date style, it lists all the sources cited in the notes at the end of the paper.
7. Which of the following options is correct about the notes-bibliography style?
- In notes-bibliography style, the elements in notes and bibliography entries follow the same general order: title, author, and facts of publication. However, authors' names are presented in standard order in notes and inverted order in bibliography entries.
- In notes-bibliography style, the elements in notes and bibliography entries follow the same general order: title, author, and facts of publication. However, authors' names are presented in inverted order in notes and standard order in bibliography entries.
- In notes-bibliography style, the elements in notes and bibliography entries follow the same general order: author, title, and facts of publication. However, authors' names are presented in standard order in notes and inverted order in bibliography entries.⁷

⁶ Ibid., 141–142.

⁷ Ibid., 149.

- In notes-bibliography style, the elements in notes and bibliography entries follow the same general order: author, title, facts of publication. However, authors' names are presented in inverted order in notes and standard order in bibliography entries.
8. To conduct dissertation research, the writer may prepare four documents: dissertation concept paper, prospectus, dissertation, and manuscript. Which of the following options best describes the definition of the manuscript?
- Dissertation manuscript is the final presentation of the design, execution, and the interpretation of the research planned in the dissertation prospectus.
- Dissertation manuscript is the complete plan for executing the dissertation and is built upon the dissertation concept paper.
- Dissertation manuscript is a brief research proposal which outlines what might be studied in the proposed dissertation, why it needs to be studied, and how it might be studied.
- Dissertation manuscript is a concise presentation of the literature review, research questions, research method, findings, discussion of the findings, and research implications.**⁸
9. Which of the following options best explains the relationship between literature analysis and research question(s)?

⁸ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition, (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 1–2.

- Literature analysis involves identifying content gaps in prior research and problems with the methods used in earlier research. Research question(s) can fill only some of the gaps indicated in the literature analysis, and the unexamined research questions stemming from the literature analysis should be included in the suggestions for future research.⁹
- Literature analysis involves identifying content gaps in prior research and problems with the methods used in earlier research. Research question(s) cannot fill the gaps indicated in the literature analysis, and the unexamined research questions stemming from the literature analysis should not be included in the suggestions for future research.
- Literature analysis involves identifying content gaps in prior research and problems with the methods used in earlier research. Research question(s) can fill all of the gaps indicated in the literature analysis, and the unexamined research questions stemming from the literature analysis should be included in the suggestions for future research.
- Literature analysis involves identifying content gaps in prior research and problems with the methods used in earlier research. Research question(s) can fill only some of the gaps indicated in the literature analysis, and the unexamined research questions stemming from the literature analysis should not be mentioned anymore.

⁹ Ibid., 32.

10. The Bluebook defines the standard to make citations of cases. The citation standard is different from the standard of the textual sentence. Which of the following options correctly applies both textual and citation standards for using legal cases?

- In a textual sentence, “Southern Pacific Co. v Jensen, 244 U.S. 205 (1917)”; In a citation, “S. Pac. Co. v. Jensen 244 U.S. 205, 225-26 (1917) (Pitney, J., dissenting)”.¹⁰
- In a textual sentence, “S. Pac. Co. v. Jensen 244 U.S. 205, 225-26 (1917) (Pitney, J., dissenting)”; In a citation, “Southern Pacific Co. v Jensen, 244 U.S. 205 (1917)”.
- In a textual sentence, “Southern Pacific Co. v Jensen”; In a citation, “S. Pac. Co. v. Jensen 244 U.S. 205, 225-26 (1917) (Pitney, J., dissenting)”.
- In a textual sentence, “Southern Pacific Co. v Jensen, 244 U.S. 205 (1917)”; In a citation, “S. Pac. Co. v. Jensen 244 U.S. 205, 225-26, 1917”.

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¹⁰ Mary Miles Prince, *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, Nineteenth Edition (Cambridge, Massachusetts: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2010), 89.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.